

JURISPRUDENCE

SOME FEATURES OF THE FIGHT WITH CORRUPTION IN THE REPUBLIC OF KAZAKHSTAN

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Abstract

The article is devoted to the current problem of combating not only in the Republic of Kazakhstan, but also all over the world. The authors reveal the goals, objectives and main conditions for effective and systemic counteraction to corruption. Special attention is given to the main factors of contributing to its manifestations in modern conditions.

Keywords: Corruption, anti-corruption, state, politics, public function.

In his message to the people of Kazakhstan "Economic course of fair Kazakhstan," President of the Republic of Kazakhstan Kassym-Zhomarta Tokayev emphasized that the country aims to create a fair state with equal opportunities and progress. He noted that Kazakhstan strives to become an effective country where law and order reign, as well as developing a culture of dialogue, responsibility and solidarity.

The problem of corruption exists all over the world and impedes socio-economic development. It manifests itself in different ways in different countries, but the main essence remains: the abuse of official position and authority for personal gain. Most often this is expressed in bribery and the use of official position for selfish purposes.

The problem of anti-corruption has existed for a long time and was discussed by ancient philosophers. Aristotle considered the fight against corruption one of the ways to increase state stability: "The main thing in the government of the state is to arrange everything in such a way that it is impossible for officials to enrich themselves". Plato also noted that greed is one of the most important social vices, which is unacceptable not only for rulers but also for warriors.

Even in Roman law, the word "corruptio" had several meanings, including bribery and destruction. Each state faces unique characteristics and challenges in combating corruption, which makes it difficult to develop effective countermeasures.

The main goal of combating corruption is its elimination in society. The Republic of Kazakhstan is designed to achieve this goal by solving the following tasks: creating an atmosphere of intolerance to corruption in society, identifying the conditions and reasons contributing to corruption offenses and eliminating them, strengthening cooperation among anti-corruption subjects, developing international cooperation to combat corruption, as well as identifying, preventing and investigating corruption offenses.

When studying the causes, conditions and consequences of corruption, it is necessary to take into account the local mentality, national and religious peculiarities, as well as the level of legal culture.

An effective fight against corruption requires accountability and control of state bodies to the public, independence and fairness of the judiciary, clear and simple laws worthy of application, meritocracy in the state's personnel policy, transparency of state procedures and zero tolerance for corruption in society.

Lack of transparency in decision-making affecting important public issues, lack of civil control and lack of regard for public opinion in the activities of the state machine lead to excessive bureaucracy, administrative barriers and abuse of power, which contributes to an increase in corruption manifestations.

Despite the qualitative update of basic legislative documents, the issues of proper application of the law remain unresolved in the organizational and legal aspect. It is necessary to use all means to prevent corrupt practices, as well as to strengthen preventive work. Attention should be paid to the activities of local authorities, as they ensure the satisfaction of the daily needs of citizens. In the activities of the special anti-corruption body, it is necessary to maintain a balance between its law enforcement and regulatory functions.

Conflicts of interest in the performance of government functions are one of the serious causes of corruption in the public sector. Conducting a detailed analysis of the mechanisms for the implementation of government functions, including public services, will help identify and eliminate corruption factors [5].

According to some opinions, the fight against corruption comes down only to countering bribery. However, this position is most likely incorrect. Bribery is the most gross and socially dangerous type of corruption crime. Therefore, it is right to pay great attention to the fight against bribery as part of the overall fight against corruption. Recently, there has been an increase in bribery. Every year, the number of bribery facts is growing. However, not all cases reach the court. The number of bribery cases heard by the courts is always

slightly lower than the number of criminal bribery cases initiated. Nevertheless, it is possible to get an upward or downward trend in the number of bribery cases from court statistics.

In his message to the people of Kazakhstan, President Kassym-Jomart Tokayev notes that it is necessary to ensure the rule of law and the quality of justice. This requires urgent renewal and improvement of the judiciary. Judges must be highly qualified, honest and incorruptible. First of all, it is necessary to ensure the equal status of all judges and reduce their dependence on their superior colleagues [6].

One of the problems of combating corruption in government is the close connection between the political (or state) and economic elites. The interaction of the public and private sectors of the economy is still noticeable, especially during the reform period. The rapid development of the private sector was to be accompanied by tough legislation and practices capable of protecting the private sector from government interference and allowing public authority to monitor compliance with the rule of law.

In Kazakhstan, active work continues to eradicate corruption, which is becoming more systematic. The basis of such activities is the demand of the head of state for the steady responsibility of all citizens, regardless of their posts, past merits or public status.

The Kazakh authorities themselves are worried about the loss of public support. The need to maintain their legitimacy through the conduct of elections makes the authorities take care of strengthening their position. The fight against corruption has become one of the effective tools for solving this problem. Representatives of all political parties actively use anti-corruption rhetoric. However, until now, all measures to limit corruption were either symbolic or partial in nature. Unfortunately, our politicians do not realize that everything hidden eventually becomes clear, and if they have chosen a political career, they must be honest and decent.

To develop an effective anti-corruption system, it is necessary first to identify the main factors contributing to the manifestation of corruption in modern conditions. Nowadays, the most relevant of them are the imperfection of industry legislation, whose norms applied in practice often create conditions for corruption crimes, especially for those who do not understand legal intricacies. The lack of transparency of government and corporate governance is also an important factor. The process of making managerial decisions remains closed, even in cases where these decisions affect the rights and legitimate interests of citizens. In addition, there are corruption risks in the provision of public services associated with the direct interaction of officials with the population. Another significant factor is the low level of legal culture, both among the general population and among public sector workers, which allows dishonest employees to use it for selfish purposes. The lack of comprehensive and targeted information work on the formation of an anti-corruption model of behavior and an atmosphere of rejection of corruption is another factor. It is also worth noting the insufficient level of remuneration for some categories of civil servants and the lack of social guarantees in public service. It is

important to note that without active public support, anti-corruption measures taken from above have a limited effect. It is necessary that every citizen of Kazakhstan treats corruption with zero tolerance, and honesty and integrity become the norm of behavior. To achieve the desired results, it is necessary to introduce an anti-corruption culture among the population and create a persistent immunity to corruption. Every Kazakhstani and every family should understand that the fight against corruption is the task of the whole society. Working with the younger generation plays a fundamentally important role in the formation of an anti-corruption culture not only in the Republic of Kazakhstan, but also in other countries. The implementation of anti-corruption standards of behavior from the very early childhood will eliminate this social evil. In addition, it is important to educate a person in the spirit of Kazakhstani patriotism and rejection of corruption. All educational institutions, state bodies and public organizations should include anti-corruption courses in their training programs. Qualified specialists of various industries on a professional basis should carry out the implementation of this process. The media play an important role in shaping public rejection of corruption, motivating Kazakhstanis to take an active civic position and actively counteract corruption. Current legislation and legal institutions have untapped anti-corruption potential, and this potential should be used to the maximum in the implementation of foreign models and experience. Frequent changes in regulatory acts, the presence of low-quality laws with many reference norms that allow bureaucratic arbitrariness - all this is a source of corruption. One of the directions of the preventive fight against corruption is the creation of legislation that prevents corrupt transactions of civil servants. This requires a mandatory analysis of the corruption of legislation to identify the most typical manifestations of corruption in the text of the law. An excellent example is the order on the rules for encouraging persons who have reported the fact of a corruption offense or otherwise help against corruption. [7].

Corruption is not only a violation of the law. It is also a undermining of confidence in the effectiveness of the state and a direct threat to national security. We must dramatically strengthen the fight against corruption, including improving anti-corruption legislation, in order to achieve our ultimate goal of eliminating corruption as a phenomenon [8].

Ensuring transparency and strengthening all forms of control over the activities of state bodies and authorities, as well as the possibility of obtaining timely information about the work of the state apparatus are one of the conditions for anti-corruption activities. The responsibility of print publishers and the media for the accuracy of their publications and speeches is also important. Today, journalism is required based on facts, arguments, serious and professional analysis, as well as a positive approach. It is necessary to more clearly define the scope, scope and competence of state bodies, eliminate duplication and determine the official functions of civil servants as accurately as possible. In this direction, quite constructive work has been carried out

recently (such as contests for filling posts of public administrative officials, which are an effective means of preventing corruption offenses).

The gradual implementation of the anti-corruption program will make it possible at the first stage to strengthen social and political stability in the country, increase public confidence in the state authorities, protect citizens from corruption, develop anti-corruption consciousness in society, and at the second stage - to activate non-governmental organizations, political parties and public associations in the implementation of anti-corruption policy, strengthen international cooperation in the fight against corruption and raise the prestige of the state in the international arena.

Many researchers, both foreign and Kazakh, indicate that the majority of the population treats corruption with some kind of loyalty, not understanding its danger. This hinders the successful fight against this phenomenon. In this regard, it should be noted that corruption causes huge, sometimes irreparable harm to the public interests, the interests of the state and individual citizens. This manifests itself in the following possible consequences:

- Corruption prevents the state from achieving its goals (for example, appointment for a bribe leads to a decrease in the efficiency of government bodies and institutions and causes huge losses);
- Corruption leads to a rise in the cost of the state apparatus (since ultimately, bribery is reflected in the taxpayer, and he is forced to pay more for services);
- Corrupt management personnel are not prepared to compromise their personal interests for the prosperity of society and the state;
- Corruption destroys justice, since the truth belongs to someone who has more money and fewer moral prohibitions;
- Corruption is a threat to democracy because it deprives the people of moral incentives to participate in elections.

Research shows that corruption in the public service in both developed and developing countries takes roughly the same forms and covers the same areas of activity. The areas most susceptible to corruption are:

- public procurement;
 - operations with land plots;
 - collection of taxes;
 - appointment to responsible posts in state bodies.
- As in other areas of activity, the most susceptible to corruption are:
- licensing and registration of business activities (including banking);
 - issuing permits for placement of securities and conducting banking operations with public funds;
 - obtaining loans (including state targeted loans);
 - customs clearance of imported goods;
 - obtaining export quotas;
 - construction and repair at the expense of state funds;
 - recruitment to high-paying or positions that allow you to receive significant illegal income in state

and local bodies (customs authorities, tax inspectorates, police traffic safety units).

The anti-corruption strategy of Kazakhstan is continuously improving taking into account the requests of society, national practice and advanced foreign experience. Within the framework of this process, the national preventive mechanism and public monitoring commissions are actively functioning. In addition; a national committee of public trust was established under the President of the Republic of Kazakhstan [9].

It is important to note that the need to take effective measures in the fight against corruption is critical. Otherwise, the problem, which began with criminal, economic and social aspects, can turn into a political problem and acquire the scale of national disaster, threatening the constitutional structure of the country. That is why in his message to the people of Kazakhstan, President of the Republic of Kazakhstan Kassym-Jomart Tokayev focused on the need to change the public consciousness and values of citizens, since "political and economic reforms alone are not enough to build a fair Kazakhstan. First of all, a change in the public consciousness and aspirations of citizens is required, without this all the rest of the work will be in vain.[1]

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